

LEARNER CENTERED APPROACH AS A MODERN WAY OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7549532>

Annotation: to show how to use effective techniques based on learner centered approach in teaching B1 level learners.

Key words: learner-centered approach, student-centered learning, exit skills, domains

English is crucial for communicative purposes to meet the demands of globalization and to deal with the growing local, national and international demands for English skills. However, there was debate that majority of high school graduates cannot speak English properly (Alonzo, 2014). Then, it was a need of an approach to establish a comfortable and low low threat learning environment for the purpose of second language acquisition. Nunan (1991) wrote that success (in speaking) is measured in terms of the ability to carry out a conversation in the (target) language. Hence, in order to enable learners to speak English fluently, a teaching approach is needed. Student centered learning. Collins and O'Brien (2003) clarified it as an instructional approach in which students influence the content, activities, material, an pace of learning. This learning model places the students as the center of learning process. The teacher provides students the opportunities to learn independently and from one another coaches them in the skills they need to do effectively.

Drawing from previous research that argued that learner-centered approaches, like cooperative learning and task-based learning, could help improve students' fluency in speaking the target language, I was eager to explore these approaches with my language classes. Learner-centered approaches like the ones aforementioned encourage language learners to use the target language while in classroom activities for language learning (Xue, 2013; Specifically, cooperative learning enables students to have peer collaboration in learning the target language (Colorado, 2015) while task-based learning gives them an avenue to use the language communicatively by doing certain tasks either individually, in pairs, or in larger groups (Nunan, 2009).

In a learner-centered approach, students are encouraged to discover for themselves whatever new learnings they will be exposed to. The culture in the student-centered classroom is that the students are made to construct knowledge through collaboration with others, synthesizing and reconstructing new information. Students, as the core of the learning process, engage in

problem solving and do interactive activities which will make them actively and productively participate, while the teachers are the coaches and facilitators of the learning process. Task-based teaching has seven principles: scaffolding, task dependency, recycling, active learning, integration of form and function, reproductive and creative language use, and the place of reflective learning. These principles allow the teacher to pre-teach some useful items to students before they do tasks that give them an opportunity to be active in the learning process, particularly in using language in communicative activities. Meanwhile, the use of language focuses more on meaning than form; however, form is learned subconsciously. This is done by students reproducing the language model handed

By the teacher. After the task, students have the chance to reflect on what they have done (Nunan, 2009). This is rooted in the theory of comprehensible input of Krashen and comprehensible output hypothesis of Student-centered learning is an` approach to education focusing on the needs of the students, rather than those of others involved in the educational process, such as teachers and administrators. Bowers and Flinders (1990) identified teacher-centered model as an industrial production in which student is a product and behaviors of “exit skills” or “out comes”. Also, the learner-centered approach means self and life-long education when teachers should change their traditional roles from teller to coordinator and from material users to teaching material providers (Baldauf & Moni, 2006). Student-centered learning is focused on the student’s needs, abilities, interests, and learning styles with the teacher as a facilitator of learning. This classroom teaching method acknowledges student voice as central to the learning experience for every learner. There are two specific approaches to students-centered learning. The first one was derived from the research on child development and involves experimentation and play as valuable forms of learning and interaction. Play involves the novel combinations of ideas, and the hypothetical outcomes of imagined events and situations. It represents the form of mental exploration, where children learn to create, work out and reflect their understanding. Another approach, where teachers uses the actual experimentation, testing and manipulation of ideas in reality, allows children to have concrete, direct feedback on the precision their ideas as they proceed in working them out. Both exploration and play are self-motivated and self-structured processes of learning that encourage children to interact and reflect on their ideas in the process of learning and acquiring new knowledge (Altan & Trombly, 2001). Here, the process of playing and doing experiment done by the

students becomes the powerful way to develop individual thinking and creativity. 2. Student Centered Learning Approach in Teaching Speaking Speaking is the most fundamental for language skill. Poonpon (2017) studying English does not only mean focusing on syntactic accuracy or grammar. Instead, it means giving opportunities to learners to use English in real life contexts. Furthermore, Brown (2007) defined speaking as a process that implies meaning, interaction and therefore communication. The context takes an important role in the interchange since it helps the participants understand the message by paying attention to the physical environment, the purpose and the experiences that people possess. Hasan (2014) found that student had perception that learning speaking was hard because the process was presented in an old way. Hence, the teachers used traditional approach that focused on grammar, vocabulary rather than communication. In other words, students were not involved in authentic communicative tasks. In order to solve this problem, SCL was the best approach to be used from the need of establishing and low threat environment, essential for mastering the full range of discourse needed for spontaneous communication. Also this study establishes that there was a need to bridge up the gap between teachers and learners to help achieve. Learner-centered learning environments recognize that the prior knowledge of learners powerfully influences future learning and thus attempt to build on prior knowledge. Assessment-centered learning environments provide opportunities for feedback and improvement throughout the learning process leading to evaluation and judgment at the end of assessment for feedback and improvement is referred to as formative assessment while assessment for conclusive evaluation and judgment is referred to as summative assessment. Nicol and Macfarlane-Dick (2006) indicate that formative assessment can promote the development of capacities and attitudes used in lifelong learning. Assessment centered learning environments also emphasize congruence between learning goals and what is assessed (National Research Council, 1999). Finally, community-centered environments recognize that individual learners take many cues and insights from learners around them, so that communitycentered learning environments facilitate purposeful interactions among learners to promote and sustain learning. For the purposes of this essay, learning environments are student-centered to the degree to which they are concurrently knowledge-centered, learner-centered, assessment-centered, and communitycentered.

Characteristics of Learner-Centered Teaching

1. Engage students in the learning process. On traditional teaching in most classes teachers are working much harder than students. Students don't develop sophisticated learning skills without the chance to practice and in most classrooms the teacher gets far more practice than the students. With Learner-Centered Teaching students have the opportunity to implement a real task and acquire 21st century skills and key competences through the process
2. Learner-centered teaching includes explicit skill instruction, students learn how to think, solve problems, decision making, team work, evaluate evidence, analyze arguments, generate hypotheses—all those learning skills essential to mastering material in the discipline. They do not assume that students pick up these skills on their own, automatically. A few students do, but not all, research shows that learning skills develop faster if they are taught explicitly along with the content.
3. Learner-centered teaching encourages students to reflect on what they are learning and how they are learning it. Learner-centered teachers talk about learning. In conversations, students write (in the e-portfolio or diary) about what they have learned, what were their difficulties and strengths . In class they may talk about their own learning and do pair assessment. They challenge student assumptions about learning and encourage them to accept responsibility for decisions they make about learning. Learner-centered teaching includes assignment components in which students reflect, analyze and critique what they are learning and how they are learning it. The goal is to make students aware of themselves as learners and to make learning skills something students want to develop. (we include the characteristics of a good learner)
4. Learner-centered teaching motivates students by giving them some control over learning processes. Teachers make most of the decisions about learning for students. Teachers decide what students should learn, how they learn it, the pace at which they learn, the conditions under which they learn and then teachers determine whether students have learned. Learner-centered teachers search out ethically responsible ways to share responsibility with students. They might give students some choice about which assignments they complete. They might make classroom agreements something students can discuss. They might let students set assignment deadlines within a given time window. They might ask students to help create assessment criteria.
5. Learner-centered teaching encourages collaboration Learner-centered teaching makes possible students can learn from and with others. The teacher has the expertise and an obligation to share it, but teachers can learn from students as well. Learner-centered teachers work to develop structures that promote shared commitments to

learning. They see learning individually and collectively as the most important goal of any educational experience. The American Psychological Association divides Learner-Centered Teaching into five domains:

1. The knowledge base. The conclusive result of decades of research on knowledge base is that what a student already knows largely determines what new information he attends to, how he organizes and represents new information, and how he filters new experiences, and even what he determines to be important or relevant. (Alexander & Murphy, 2000)
2. Strategic processing and executive control. The ability to reflect on and regulate one's thoughts and behaviors is an essential aspect of learning. Successful students are actively involved in their own learning, monitor their thinking, think about their learning, and assume responsibility for their own learning (Lambert & McCombs, 2000)
3. Motivation and affect. The benefits of learner-centered education include increased motivation for learning and greater satisfaction with school; both of these outcomes lead to greater achievement. Personal involvement, intrinsic motivation, personal commitment, confidence in one's abilities to succeed, and a perception of control over learning lead to more learning and higher achievement in school. (Alexander & Murphy, 2000)
4. Development and individual differences. Individuals progress through various common stages of development, influenced by both inherited and environmental factors.
5. Situation or context. Theories of learning that highlight the roles of active engagement and social interaction in the students' own construction of knowledge. Many environmental factors including how the teacher teaches, and how actively engaged the student is in the learning process positively or negatively influence how much and what students learn (Lambert & McCombs, 2000)

Learner-centered teaching is an approach to teaching that is increasingly being encouraged in education. Learner-centered teachers do not employ a single teaching method. This approach emphasizes a variety of different types of methods that focus on what the students are learning, it changes the role of the teachers from a provider of information to facilitating student learning. Traditional teaching often leads to students who are passive learners and who do not take responsibility for their own learning, this traditional method ("instructor-centered teaching.") In contrast with, "learner centered teaching" occurs when instructors focus on student learning. Learner-centered teaching places the emphasis on the person who is doing the learning (Weimer,

2002). Learning-centered teaching focuses on the process of learning. Both phrases identify their critical role of teaching in the learning process. The phrase student centered learning is also used, but some instructors do not like it because it appears to have a consumer focus, seems to encourage students to be more empowered, and appears to take the teacher out of the critical role (Blumberg, 2004). Student-centered teaching methods include active learning, in which students solve problems, answer questions, formulate questions of their own, discuss, explain, debate, or brainstorm during class; cooperative learning, in which students work in teams on problems and projects under conditions that assure both positive interdependence and individual accountability; and inductive teaching and learning, in which students are first presented with challenges (questions or problems) and learn the course material in the context of addressing the challenges. Inductive methods include inquiry-based learning, case-based instruction, problem-based learning, project-based learning, discovery learning, and just-in-time teaching. Student-centered methods have repeatedly been shown to be superior to the traditional teacher-centered approach to instruction, a conclusion that applies whether the assessed outcome is shortterm mastery, long-term retention, or depth of understanding of course material, acquisition of critical thinking or creative problem-solving skills, formation of positive attitudes toward the subject being taught, or level of confidence in knowledge or skills. Characteristics of Learner-Centered Teaching:

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English level B1 would be sufficient for interactions with English speakers on familiar topics. In the workplace, people at a B1 level of English are able to read simple reports on familiar topics and write simple e-mails on subjects in their field. However, a B1 level is not adequate to function fully in the workplace in English.

According to the official State Educational standards someone at the B1 level in English. They can participate in a conversation on a prepared topic (interview, validation and confirmation) and on unprepared topics (when traveling to a foreign language in the study area), in contingencies, in debates give their opinion on familiar topics (books, movies, music), share information on familiar and less familiar topics, cost negotiation and so on.

The information about B1 level illustrates they must have already had basic knowledge in English and able to speak simple structures and the volume of their interests becomes so broad.

There is a simple fact: the one who speaks more in class is the center. The students speak more than 50% of the class time -it's a student-centered class. It is clear that, it would be nice, if the teacher speaks less than one student in class. It is very hard to achieve. Fen said "Teacher who indulges in being the center of attention explaining the text closely in a more traditional grammar—translation way trying to put everything into students' heads and paying scant notice of the feelings and reactions of students. Students are just an "ignorant audience", waiting to be filled up with knowledge by the teacher. There is little cooperation between the teacher and the students and the teacher gets little feedback from listeners. I think, in this way no result in speaking skill can not be taken.

Lisaid stated that "In learner-centered teaching, the main idea behind the practice is that learning is most meaningful when topics are relevant to the students' lives, needs and interests and when the students themselves are actively engaged in creating, understanding and connecting to knowledge. Teacher shares control of the classroom and students are allowed to explore, experiment, and discover on their own. The students are given choices and are included in the decision-making process of the classroom, the focus in these classrooms is on options, rather than uniformity."

So, we also concentrate on this idea to motivate students in the audience and develops initiative for speaking, critical thinking and so on. Here, we picked up several specific points about the effectiveness of learner-centered approach for developing speaking. You can find the answer for the question whether it has more beneficial effect on speaking rather than teacher-centered approach:

- In teacher-centered approach:
- Learners are passive and respond only to environmental stimuli.
- The teacher is in charge of learning; therefore, learners just receives information.

The learners do not collaborate. The content is decided and the learning tasks are structured by the teacher. The instruction is delivered through lecturing and provision of feedback and correct answers are widely used. Student productivity is low.

The teacher Is the primary source of information and the textbook is the center of activities. Learner reads the ready information. It limits problem solving and decision making skills of students.

Mostly, passive students are out of attention than active ones in the classroom. The primary goal in the classroom is to empower learning. In this respect, in order for teachers to maintain control over students, they need to ensure that they enable the students to participate actively in the classroom. If teachers are knowledgeable in the content they present and apply motivational strategies while teaching, students maintain their attention, actively engaged in the classroom and become academically successful. For that reason, some researchers support the use of teacher-centered approach because it allows teaching students in short steps. In learner centered classrooms;

- ☒ Teachers avoid transmissions of knowledge directly.
- ☒ Students play active role in the learning process through trying “to make sense of what they are learning by relating it to prior knowledge and by discussing it with others”.
- ☒ Learners are provided opportunities to learn independently in student-centered learning and they are involved in the activities, materials and content.
- ☒ Creation of meaning comes to the fore in student-centered learning and learning is influenced by the prior knowledge.
- ☒ cooperative learning in which a group of students work together to complete a given task for that reason it enhances student-to-student interaction.
- ☒ Cooperative learning enables the students to seek for understanding.

- ☒ The search for constructing meaning and productivity leads to increased intrinsic motivation which will facilitate higher achievement in the classroom.
- ☒ Simply put, student-centered approach is based on the idea that students are engaged in knowledge construction using their experiences and actions.
- ☒ The proper implementation of student-centered instruction promotes motivation to learn, develops understanding, and facilitates knowledge retention. Cooperative learning gives students the authority to engage in the learning process.
- ☒ To accomplish tasks the students set goals and develop ideas, involve in thoughtful discourse, explore different perspectives and improve their learning.
- ☒ When learners are encouraged to create their own understanding in a classroom climate, they develop their individual responsibility.
- ☒ The implementation of discussion-oriented activities helps students deal with multiple perspectives and build a community of dignity for diverse ideas.
- ☒ Democratic principles underpinned student-centered approach. The idea of giving responsibility to students, allowing them to act effectively, and

stimulating reflective and critical thinking in the classroom enrich democratic society. Learner-centeredness is an effective pedagogy to equip students with the necessary skills to generate a more democratic society.

☒ Learners construct their own understanding by means of experiences. Furthermore, building a comfortable learning environment is an essential factor in student achievement.

☒ learner-centered classroom has funny activities.

☒ That students take an active role and present information to the others and share classroom responsibilities increase their self-confidence.

However, in learner-centered classrooms control may become difficult due to behaviour problems. Although this will be tedious, teachers can turn it to an advantage by encouraging them to increase their sense of responsibility. Mart states that “passionate teachers know that it is their role to encourage students for an active learning and concern themselves with promoting students’ intellectual and moral development”. It is recommended that teachers enhance intrinsic motivation of students in student-centered classrooms which benefits students to develop their autonomy and encourage them to make responsible choices. On the other hand, it may negatively influence students’ motivation because it encourages them to develop appropriate behaviours just to get the reward .

In conclusion, it should be noted learners’ participation is as a primary goal in speaking lessons, not receiving information, not theoretical things. Also, the initial aim raising productivity, interaction, developing communication. Definitely, students cannot construct their skills and understandings by themselves without a facilitator. However, there is the difference what a learner can do without help and what he/she can do with an accomplished peer. Without a skilled partner or adult speaking cannot be implemented by students themselves. Without teacher direction, it is not possible for learners to achieve higher learning outcomes. Moreover, reading the advantages of learner-centered approach it can be concluded that for developing speaking rather than other three skills(writing, reading, listening) critical thinking, motivation and self-confidence plays as a leading factor

References:

1. Integrating Student-Centered Learning to Promote Critical Thinking in High School Social Studies Classrooms 2013

2. Investigating the learner-centred approach in language teaching in Lesotho
3. Amelia Matsau Investigating the learner-centred approach in language teaching in Lesotho Mamonaheng Master of Education Victoria University 2007
4. Learner's centred approaches Building theoretical skills to put theory into practice
5. Learner-Centered Approaches: Their Effect on the Oral Fluency of Students
6. Learner-Centered Approaches: Why They Matter and How to Implement Them by Caroline Lawless, published on September 26, 2019
7. Lex.uz
8. Mamonaheng Amelia Matsau Master of Education, Victoria University 2007
9. Practical Law for Law Students First Edition: DRAFT COPY By Bruce A. Lasky, Michael A. Otto & Wendy Morrish (General Editors) First Edition: DRAFT COPY By Bruce A. Lasky, Michael A. Otto & Wendy Morrish page 52

